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The use of constructive alignment in the design of laboratory activities

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INTRODUCTION

Laboratory experimentation has long been considered an important component of engineering education, allowing students to explore and understand physical phenomena in a controlled environment. Despite this claimed importance there has been relatively limited research into approaches for effective engineering laboratory design, or even the intended learning objectives of laboratory activities (a key exception being an ABET colloquium which resulted in a taxonomy of thirteen laboratory learning objectives [1]). While it is generally accepted that for any teaching and learning activity thoughtful design is required to elicit demonstrated achievement against the associated learning outcomes, such thoughtful approaches are not always evident in the design of laboratory experiments where it may be assumed that by simply viewing the physical phenomena students understanding of the associated theory is automatically improved. The application of thoughtful laboratory design processes is required if the significant potential educational outcomes are to be achieved through this important educational modality.

In this paper we explore the relevance and use of constructive alignment as a guiding framework for laboratory learning activity design. Constructive alignment promotes an approach that combines constructionism in learning and alignment in teaching and

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assessment. Constructive alignment “makes the students do the real work” with the instructor simply acting as a coach or facilitator to assist students to engage with the learning opportunity and environment that supports the learning activities [2, p27]. It commences from an articulation of the intended learning outcomes, and then uses these to drive the design of assessment methods and learning activities. Given that laboratory experiments are inherently experiential, there is a risk that their design focuses on the learning activities to the exclusion of consideration of the educational drivers. We analyse an exemplar undergraduate engineering laboratory activity guide and consider the extent to which it focuses on the equipment and activity versus the extent to which it makes explicit both the learning outcomes and the assessment criteria. We then extend this by proposing a framework, based on constructive alignment, for the design of laboratory experiments that more directly address designed learning outcomes.

1 LABORATORY EXPERIMENT DESIGN

1.1 Educational Laboratories

Laboratory-based experimentation has long been considered an important element of education in the physical sciences and engineering. Allowing students to explore physical phenomena in a controlled environment through various forms of carefully designed first-hand practical work, including experimentation, can potentially support effective learning and motivate students' engagement while fulfilling specific curriculum requirements [3], [4]. This recognition has become so embedded, that the inclusion of experimental laboratories into the curricula is essentially mandated in many accreditation frameworks (e.g. from Engineers Australia accreditation criteria: “3.2.4.5. *Practical and ‘Hands-On’ Experience: There must be substantial hands-on practical experience manifested through specifically designed laboratory activities, investigatory assignments and project work...*” [5]).

Despite this recognition of the value of laboratory experimentation, and the close to universal utilisation of laboratory experimentation in engineering degree programs, there is surprisingly little research that focuses specifically on the design of laboratory experiments and how this design might differ from more general educational design. As long ago as 1982, aspects that were being neglected in research into laboratory education had been identified [6], with most of the elements identified at that time still to be adequately considered. Of particular note is the paucity of research into the types of learning outcomes that might be suitable for laboratory experiments. One key exception is the work that emerged out of a 2002 ABET Colloquy on laboratory education. This resulted in the articulation of a taxonomy of thirteen learning objectives [1] that might be relevant to laboratory activities.

The ABET taxonomy has been subsequently used in exploring comparisons of the level of achievement of learning in laboratories (see, for example, [7], [8]) but not explicitly in the design of laboratories. Indeed, whilst there is a significant volume of work in the literature outlining the technical design of, or student responses to, specific laboratory experiments there is very limited work that has been reported on the pedagogic design of experiments. Where such work has occurred, the focus has generally been on specific characteristics rather than broader design approaches. For example Terkowsky and Heartel [9] explored the types of objectives and activities that might be suited to developing creativity.

By developing a clearer understanding of laboratory experiment design approaches we can potentially improve the quality of the student learning outcomes. One possible approach that is worth consideration is the use of constructive alignment.

1.2 Constructive Alignment

The concepts underlying constructive alignment were originally developed by Tyler in 1949 [10], but the main formulation was carried out much later by Biggs [11]. Essentially constructive alignment (CA) promotes an approach that commences from an articulation of the intended learning outcomes, and then uses these in driving the design of both assessment approaches and learning activities so that all three components – objectives, assessment and activities – are appropriately aligned. CA could potentially provide a mechanism for ensuring that laboratory experiment design does not focus on the nature of the activity to the exclusion of broader objectives and assessment.

CA promotes an approach that combines constructionism in learning and alignment in teaching and assessment. It “makes students do the real work” with the instructor acting as a coach or facilitator to assist students to engage with the learning opportunity and environment that supports the learning activities [2, p27]. Biggs comments that surface approaches to learning arise from a focus on getting a task out of the way as easily as possible while appearing to achieve the learning outcomes. He suggests that the nonalignment of teaching and assessment methods promote surface approaches. Hence when students behave and respond to our learning activities with a surface approach we need to improve the alignment of our learning outcomes, assessment methods and teaching and learning activities. Conversely, deep approaches to learning are associated with positive feelings, a belief that what is being learnt is important, valuable and meaningful [2]. Students who learn deeply often feel excited, enjoyment and exhilarated by the challenges associated with their learning.

Hence in the context of laboratories it is important to consider how students behave and respond to our laboratory learning outcomes, activity design and assessment. Are students able to simply join the dots and report what they have seen or are they required to critically evaluate and interpret the theory to explain their observations. Are they excited about what they discover, curious to understand or simply focused on completing the assessment task at the desired level of achievement by taking the path of least effort and resistance?

Assessment defines what is important for students to learn. Biggs stresses that activities are verbs and should be used to enable students to learn both how to, and what is required to, demonstrate achievement at different levels (grades) described by the learning outcomes. Hence grade descriptors are an important part of constructive alignment. Even with the best aligned educational design we cannot assume that students will automatically know how to engage with the learning outcomes activities and assessments. Hence scaffolding should be used to explain to students [12]:

- i. why the assessment activity was designed this way;
- ii. what learning opportunities the activity provides students;
- iii. how students can evaluate their learning from the activity; and
- iv. how it is going to impact on their reality (enable them to see the world differently).

CA has been explored relatively extensively in the context of engineering education (see [13] for a good example) but has seen very little use in supporting laboratory experiment design. The exceptions to this are a small number of specific cases where CA has been used to *evaluate* the design of laboratory experiments. For example Smith [14] used CA to explore issues of misalignment in the design of laboratory experiences, and Bhathal, Sharma, and Mendez [15] have also used CA to carry out an educational analysis of a specific laboratory. These previous studies do suggest that CA may be a useful analysis and design tool. In

particular, by exploring the concepts that underpin CA we can identify a range of critical elements that can either be the basis of an evaluation for an existing laboratory experience (Table 1) or can guide the design of a new laboratory experience (Table 5).

Table 1. Laboratory Design Evaluation

Focus	Evaluation questions
1. Learning Outcomes	
<i>1a. Outcomes Description</i>	Are the learning outcomes clearly described?
<i>1b. Outcomes Levels</i>	Have levels of achievement of the learning outcomes been identified?
2. Assessment Tasks	
<i>2a. Assessment Description</i>	Are the assessment tasks clearly described?
<i>2c. Assessment Levels</i>	Do the tasks allow for demonstration of the different levels of achievement?
<i>2b. Assessment-LO Alignment</i>	Are the assessment tasks appropriately aligned to the stated learning outcomes?
3. Learning Activities	
<i>3a. Activity Description</i>	Have the learning activities been clearly described?
<i>3b. Activity-LO alignment</i>	Are the learning activities explicitly connected to the learning objectives?
<i>3b. Activity-Assess alignment</i>	Are the learning activities explicitly connected to the assessment tasks?
<i>3c. Activity levels</i>	Do the learning activities provide opportunities for demonstrating levels of achievement against the assessment tasks?

2 CASE STUDY ANALYSIS: LOGIC ANALYZER LABORATORY

To illustrate the potential for Constructive Alignment to assist in the evaluation and design of laboratory experiences, we apply the approach to a case study based on a microprocessor laboratory activity described in <https://goo.gl/gjExV3>. The experiment aims to introduce students to the use of a logic analyser for debugging microprocessor systems. Students are first required to set up an experiment board with a Z80 microprocessor and connect it to a logic analyser. They then use the logic analyser to observe the operation of a known program and analyse the data. Students are finally given an unknown program which they are required to decode using the logic analyser in order to decipher what the program is doing. The experiment instructions consist of an introduction describing the purpose of the experiment, a detailed background section which covers required knowledge, and then step by step instructions guiding students through the set up and execution of the experiment. The final instructions are for the students to complete a report describing their results and answering the questions that are posed. An analysis of the information presented in the laboratory instructions according to the criteria in Table 1 is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Logic Analyzer experiment - evaluation

Focus / Evaluation Questions	Evaluation observations
1. Learning Outcomes	
<i>1a. Outcomes Description</i> Are the learning outcomes clearly described?	Yes, partially. The experiment instructions include a description of what students should be able to do by the end of the lab:

	<p><i>“This lab will be your introduction to the use of a logic analyzer to study the operation of complex digital circuitry in real time at speeds up to 500 MHz. By the end of this lab, you will be able to:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Connect a logic analyzer to a microprocessor system</i> • <i>Set-up the acquisition system of the logic analyzer</i> • <i>Trigger the logic analyzer on a specific state event</i> • <i>Disassemble the bus cycle information to decode the instruction and data flow of several simple Z80 programs..</i> • <i>Use a logic analyzer to debug your project design”</i> <p>These are however presented in such a way that students would expect each point to have equal relevance which is not the intention of the teacher who is focussed on students learning to decode the instructions of the microprocessor.</p> <p>In addition, the description of the experiment clarifies that students are using the Z80 microprocessor as substitute for the 68008 microprocessor they will use in the rest of their labs. This is because the Z80 has no features such as prefetching - what is seen on the logic analyser is exactly what the processor is doing. Implicit in this is that students are expected to take what they learn in the experiment on the Z80, and understand how it may apply to the 68008 microprocessor. This learning outcome has not been clearly described.</p>
<p><i>1b. Outcomes Levels</i></p> <p>Have levels of achievement of the learning outcomes been identified?</p>	<p>No.</p> <p>The learning outcomes described do not allow for different levels of achievement, rather they are binary, students achieve them or not.</p>
<p>2. Assessment Tasks</p>	
<p><i>2a. Assessment Description</i></p> <p>Are the assessment tasks clearly described?</p>	<p>Yes, partially.</p> <p>The assessment is in the form of a report with a breakdown of what should be included in the document, however there is no weighting given to any of the components of the report.</p> <p><i>“The paper should have an introduction, a section on what your procedure and process, a section on what you observed, and any conclusions.”</i></p> <p><i>“Your lab report should include:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Answers to any questions posed in the report</i> 2. <i>A screen capture of your timing diagram that you used to measure the bus cycle timing</i> 3. <i>An analysis of the measured timing from your circuit versus the published specifications, being sure to cite your references</i> 4. <i>A printout of your Excel spreadsheet after filtering</i> 5. <i>You disassembled instruction listing</i> 6. <i>A description of what the program does and your assembly language source file</i> 7. <i>A bibliography of any resources you consulted, as well as citing any assistance you received from your classmates”</i>
<p><i>2c. Assessment Levels</i></p> <p>Do the tasks allow for demonstration of the different levels of achievement?</p>	<p>Yes, in terms of the quality of the written report students may demonstrate different levels of achievement.</p>
<p><i>2b. Assessment-LO Alignment</i></p> <p>Are the assessment tasks appropriately aligned to the stated learning outcomes?</p>	<p>Not clearly. In this case the assessment is described in the form of a report which does not clearly align with the outcomes of “connect a logic analyser” and “set up ... the logic analyser”.</p>

3. Learning Activities	
<p><i>3a. Activity Description</i></p> <p>Have the learning activities been clearly described?</p>	<p>Yes.</p> <p>This is described by a series of steps:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Steps 1-7: Procedure to set up the board and connect it to the logic analyser</i> • <i>Steps 8-11: Procedure to use the logic analyser to take and store a trace from the board</i> • <i>Step 12: A description of the program running on the microprocessor and how it relates to what is observed on the logic analyser</i> • <i>Steps 13 and 14: Procedure to use the logic analyser to collect trace and analyse it to decode an unknown program</i>
<p><i>3b. Activity-LO alignment</i></p> <p>Are the learning activities explicitly connected to the learning objectives?</p>	<p>Yes partially.</p> <p>For the articulated learning outcomes, many are explicitly connected to the learning activities and would be achieved through the successful completion of the steps, such as “Connect a logic analyzer to a microprocessor system”. The final learning outcome (using a logic analyser for debugging) is not covered in this experiment.</p> <p>The learning outcome not clearly described (that students are able to understand how this learning will apply to other microprocessors) has not been included in any of the learning activities.</p>
<p><i>3b. Activity-Assess alignment</i></p> <p>Are the learning activities explicitly connected to the assessment tasks?</p>	<p>Yes.</p> <p>The assessed report explicitly connects the learning activities to assessment as it is expected to contain information gathered through the learning activities.</p>
<p><i>3c. Activity levels</i></p> <p>Do the learning activities provide opportunities for demonstrating levels of achievement against the assessment tasks?</p>	<p>No.</p> <p>The learning activities do not allow for students to demonstrate different levels of achievement.</p>

The conclusion from this analysis is that whilst the experiment is an interesting activity which exposes students to debugging microprocessors, the quality of the outcomes are potentially compromised by a lack of clarity in the intended learning outcomes in terms of their importance and the fact that there is an important ‘implicit’ learning outcome not clearly expressed to students. Taken together with the corresponding lack of weighting information for the assessment and the fact that there is no assessment of whether students have understood to the level that they can transfer their knowledge to other microprocessors, it is possible that the learning outcomes from this laboratory are not in line with the teachers’ expectations.

3 DESIGN FRAMEWORK

The above example illustrate that CA can be used to gain insights into the design of existing laboratories, but we can also turn this around and reframe the evaluation questions into a set of design steps in order to guide the laboratory experience design process.

Space limitations in the paper prevent a detailed case study from being presented, but Figure 1 presents the key design stages and the sequencing of the design. This process adheres to that defined for Constructive Alignment: beginning by specifying the laboratory learning outcomes; then moving on to specifying how those learning outcomes will be assessed; and then finally determining the learning activities that will be carried out. At each stage the alignment is assessed and, where necessary, the process is iterated to ensure appropriate alignment is achieved.

Figure 1. Laboratory Design Stages

4 SUMMARY

Constructive Alignment has been widely shown to be a valuable approach to educational design, and yet there has been very limited exploration of the application of CA to the design of laboratory experiences. An analysis of existing student information on laboratory experiments shows that most student guides focus on describing the experimental activities to be carried out and often fail to provide clarity in the intended learning outcomes that are being targeted or connect these to assessment activities that allow students to assess their progress in achievement of those learning outcomes. We have argued that the application of CA to laboratory experiments will allow much more effective design. Future work in this area would focus on assessing the extent to which improved student learning outcomes can be achieved through the application of CA.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. D. Feisel and A. J. Rosa, "The Role of the Laboratory in Undergraduate Engineering Education," *J. Eng. Educ.*, vol. 94, no. 1, pp. 121–130, 2005.
- [2] J. Biggs, *Teaching for Quality Learning at University: What The Student Does*, 2nd Ed. Philadelphia, PA: Society for Research into Higher Education: Open University Press, 2003.
- [3] A. Hofstein and V. Lunetta, "The laboratory in science education: Foundations for the twenty-first century," *Sci. Educ.*, vol. 88, no. 1, pp. 28–54, Jan. 2004.
- [4] M. Pickering, "The teaching laboratory through history," *J. Chem. Educ.*, vol. 70, no. 9, pp. 699–700, Sep. 1993.
- [5] A. Bradley, "Accreditation Management System - Education Programs at the Level of Professional Engineer - G02: Accreditation Criteria Guidelines," Canberra, Australia, 2008.
- [6] A. Hofstein and V. Lunetta, "The role of the laboratory in science teaching: Neglected aspects of research," *Rev. Educ. Res.*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 201–217, 1982.
- [7] J. E. Corter, S. K. Esche, C. Chassapis, J. Ma, and J. V. Nickerson, "Process and learning outcomes from remotely-operated, simulated, and hands-on student laboratories," *Comput. Educ.*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 2054–2067, Nov. 2011.
- [8] E. Lindsay and M. Good, "Effects of laboratory access modes upon learning outcomes," *Educ. IEEE Trans.*, vol. 48, no. 4, pp. 619–631, 2005.
- [9] C. Terkowsky and T. Heartel, "On Learning Objectives and Learning Activities to Foster Creativity in the Engineering Lab," in *2014 International Conference on Interactive Collaborative Learning (ICL)*, 2014, pp. 923–935.
- [10] R. W. Tyler, *Basic principles of curriculum and instruction*. 1949.
- [11] J. Biggs, "Enhancing teaching through constructive alignment," *High. Educ.*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 347–364, 1996.
- [12] K. Willey and A. Gardner, "Collaborative learning frameworks to promote a positive learning culture," in *Frontiers in Education Conference, FIE2012*, 2012, pp. 1–6.
- [13] S. Nightingale, A. Carew, and J. Fung, "Application of constructive alignment principles to Engineering education : have we really changed ?," in *AAEE - Annual Conference of Australasian Association for Engineering Education*, 2007, pp. 1–9.
- [14] R. Smith, "Alignment of intended learning outcomes, curriculum and assessment in a middle school science program," Edith Cowan University, 2012.
- [15] R. Bhathal, M. D. Sharma, and A. Mendez, "Educational analysis of a first year engineering physics experiment on standing waves: Based on the ACELL approach," *Eur. J. Phys.*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 23–35, 2010.